

CHANGES OF LANGUAGES: FACTORS, REASONS AND INTERACTIONS

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Annotation: In the given article, following results can be discussed: every language is unique and while investigating it illustrates various ways of changes because of human intervention and participation, linguistic analysis and different factors of language changing such as language learning, social differentiation, natural process in usage and language contact.

Key words: Language change, studying synchronically, reviewing diachronically, generation, assimilation, dissimilation, relatedness hypothesis.

Introduction.

There thousands of languages in the world. Every language owns its own unique and interconnected history. According to some factors, languages were changed from its origin one. While investigating history of languages people divided languages' history into different stages and created language families. It can be seen that languages change across social groups and space. Generation by generation, exposure to other languages, altered languages through structure, use of language, borrowed words, sounds etc.

There are number of reasons to language change. For instance:

- Language learning: Language can be transmitted from one generation to the next. Obviously, each person re-creates lexion and grammar based on input from surrounding. That means, more experiences, more changing.
 - Social differenciation: Various social groups adopt special norms of ornamentation, clothing and gestures. Here, they can adopt their names as well. Different groups can call them in different ways and of course, this process effects on employing slangs, jargon, syntactic constructions and pronunciation.
- Natural process in usage: Natural and casual speech generates changes such as, apocope, syncope, assimilation and dissimilation.
- Language contact: Conquest, trade and migration creates opportunities to relationship of speakers with each other. In this situation, some people can become bilingual, some change their first language in order to make it more understandable. In such situations, languages can change own constructions, sounds and borrow words.

The main part

According to the research belonging to I. Galperin recent decades have seen a major increase in the amount of influence the two models have had on each

other, especially American on British. The influence of US films and television has led to a considerable passive understanding of much American the English vocabulary in Britain, and some of this has turned into active use (as in the case of *mail*), especially among younger people. The reverse pattern is less obvious, but British films and TV programmes are seen sufficiently often in the USA to mean that a growth in awareness of UK vocabulary should not be discounted. What were originally fairly clear patterns of lexical differentiation have been obscured by borrowing on a world-wide scale.

Mihalicek (2011) also explains some information about these changes. Due to his explanation there are two types of linguistic analysis

- Studying synchronically what is happening with language and its rules and learns current phonological process;
- Reviewing diachronically what happened with phonetic or grammatical rules, how they were used in history. Why some linguistic rules were changed across the time.

Main Historical linguists investigate this process and if it is about English language history they connected it with Proto-Indo-European family which includes old Latin, Gothic, Old Persian and Sanskrit languages.

Mihalicek (2011) compares how languages changed during the period by means of comparison Old, Middle, Early Modern and Contemporary English languages. Having looked through this information we can see that in Old English there word order is free and Latin affects its pronunciation. Moreover, French influenced Middle English pronunciation. However, as German language all letters were pronounced those times. That means both languages affected pronunciation rules.

Furthermore, Modern English is different from its origin phonetic and grammar rules. Some silent letters like k - knife can be seen. Word order is very strict as well, which can not be changed in some cases.

As they were from one family tree people mutually understood each other. People who speak in one language family sometimes recognize some words. It is called interrelationship between languages. According to some factors as old languages words influenced to most of the languages in the world they became sisters and brothers. For instance, as Mihalicek (2011) points out Latin German is the mother of English language in Porto-Indo-European family tree while Spanish and French languages are sisters. People had to change some words because they could not pronounce some letters. Mihalicek (2011) calls it as relatedness hypothesis in this chapter.

In conclusion, having learnt this, some useful and clear information was acquired which compares some original points of language changes. If we review, other languages which are not border with English speaking countries or Europe but the member of Indo-European family there relatedness hypothesis can be perceived. For instance, Tajikistan is situated in the Central Asia and there majority of used languages in this continent belong to Turkish languages families. In spite of its location, Tajik people use the language of Indo-European family. In addition, there number of same words with European lexeme.

Here we can see their relativeness in some simple words:

Latin	English	French	Tajik	Russian
duo	two	du	du	Два (dva)
mater	mother	Mère	Modar	Мать (Mat)
brothe	brother	brothe	baroda	Брат (brat)

Besides this, language changes happens every time due to geographical, social and economic factors. Despite, English is the dominant language in the world its linguistic features especially, vocabulary changed gradually. Nowadays, Italian, Chinese and Japan words “supplementing” its rich vocabulary. “Pizza”, “Sushi” “Mozzarella” and others can be examples here.

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